

Preventive Practices Towards Sexually Transmitted Infections and Associated Factors Among High School Students in Gondar Town, Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are a major public health problem worldwide that causes acute illness, long-term complications, infertility, medical and psychological consequences, and death. The incidence of STIs is increasing in developing countries due to barriers related to the asymptomatic nature of most infections, a lack of simple diagnostic methods, adolescents' lack of knowledge of the seriousness of STIs, and most importantly, the inaccessibility of health service resources. Ethiopia, like many developing countries, struggles with the challenge of STIs among the youth population. High school students, in particular, represent a critical target group for interventions due to a lack of health education and the risk of engaging in risky behaviors. Hence, the objective of the study was to assess preventive practices towards STIs and associated factors among high school students in Gondar town, Ethiopia.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted from December 4, 2023 to January 6, 2024 among 214 students attending Fasiledes secondary and preparatory school. Data was summarized using frequency with percentage. To identify factors associated with preventive practices, a binary logistic regression analysis was run where adjusted odds ratio with 95% CI and p-value of ≤ 0.05 was used.

Results: Among the 214 participants, 89.7% had heard about STIs. Of these participants, 54.7% demonstrated good knowledge, and 62.1% displayed positive attitudes towards STIs. However, only 46 (21.5%) participants practiced risky sexual behavior. Among those engaging in risky behavior, 60.9% engaged in sexual intercourse under the influence of substances, 39.1% had multiple sexual partners, and 19.6% did not use a condom during sexual intercourse. The odds of engaging in at least one risky behavior were significantly higher among students who believed that STIs are not transmitted through blood, prostitution is not a risky behavior, having an STI co-infection is not a risk, and having a single partner is not a preventive method for STIs.

Conclusions: Despite a high awareness of STIs and positive attitudes, a significant portion of students engaged in risky sexual behaviors. These behaviors were more prevalent among students with misconceptions about STI transmission and prevention. Prioritizing youth reproductive health through comprehensive sexual health education is crucial. Strategies should build upon existing knowledge and positive attitudes to create more effective interventions that help students avoid risky behaviors. Further research is necessary to understand the disconnect between knowledge and behavior, ensuring educational programs effectively translate knowledge into safer decision-making.

Key words: Sexually Transmitted Infections, High-school students, Risky Sexual Practice, Ethiopia

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